

BIOcean5D collective plankton time series with the Lamprey metabarcoding system: - a RoadMap-

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Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
1.0	E.Legeay, N.Henry, D.Guiffant, C.de Vargas - SBRoscoff	First version sent to all workshop participants.	06.06.2025

- ❖ Logsheets instructions:
https://zenodo.org/records/15739243?token=eyJhbGciOiJIUzUxMiJ9.eyJpZCI6IjcxYTdlZTg2LWRjNjMtNDlmMi1iYTViLTc2MWNkY2ZjMDkxYSIsImRhdGEiOnt9LCJyYW5kb20iOiI3ZWwWzQwNzFIYThlYzgyYzYzNDgyZjhmZDkxNzZmYSJ9.yui8H7Zm9XA5-E-f0BSlyWnk_dRaiHfwMp65o8heKxK4cXkS41zUs0pS3Sb
- ❖ Logsheets:
https://zenodo.org/records/15739303?token=eyJhbGciOiJIUzUxMiJ9.eyJpZCI6ImRkMGFhNjEwLTlhYjEtNGYyYi1hOTU5LTliMTg2ZTU2ZTk1ZCIsImRhdGEiOnt9LCJyYW5kb20iOiIwNGRmNDhhOTFkNDdlYTJmYzVhYzYwMmY1NWJlYTU5NyJ9.qVf5G04nT1u0mCFjecz2iKe77mM5tnwHntrOwNQzmxA3a0KOrIN_fKShCLw

For any questions, suggestions, or experience sharing, we invite you to use the **Slack platform**.

Four dedicated communication channels have been made available to you. We strongly encourage all exchanges to take place through these channels, so that interactions with the Roscoff team or among participants can benefit the entire community involved in the project.

More details are available below in this document in a dedicated section.

Sampling & Data protocol

When?

Starting in June 2025, please collect samples from your local site **once every two weeks for a duration of one year**, resulting in 26 sampling events. You may begin slightly earlier or later if more convenient, provided that sampling is conducted regularly over the course of the year. The objective is to capture seasonal variability at each local site.

For sites influenced by significant tidal fluctuations, please aim to sample **at high tide**.

We acknowledge that sampling may be challenging at certain times of the year in some places (e.g., sea ice, storms). If you need to miss some sampling events, please compensate by increasing sampling frequency during ecologically relevant periods (e.g., along a bloom) to ensure a total of 26 samples are collected over the year.

Approximately halfway through the sampling period, you will be requested to send your samples to the *Station Biologique de Roscoff* for DNA metabarcoding processing, including extraction, amplification, library preparation, and sequencing at Genoscope. Further details regarding sample shipment are provided in the section below. Samples will have to be sent with their local sampling permits.

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Where?

The objective is to sample **coastal water columns** at sites with easy access to facilitate fieldwork. A marina, such as the one in Roscoff where participants of the 2nd and 3rd workshops practiced sampling, is ideal. These locations are sheltered and provide access to several meters of depth by foot. Sample from the sheltered side of the marina. If this is not feasible, sampling by boat is acceptable; however, please make every effort to sample as close to the coast as possible.

How?

All teams will sample **micro- to meso-plankton** (20 μm to 2 mm) from **coastal water columns** using the standardized [sampling protocol](#) introduced during the Roscoff training workshop. **Vertical plankton net tows** should be performed from near the seafloor—without contacting it, to avoid sediment resuspension—up to the surface. Please record the maximum towing depth accurately (with marks on the rope), as it is necessary for estimating the theoretical volume of sampled water.

The concentrated sample from the cod-end should be pre-filtered through a **2 mm** (2,000 μm) **mesh sieve**[#] as it is poured into a 500 mL bottle. This pre-filtered sample is then processed through a **47 mm diameter, 10 μm pore-size filter membrane** installed in the Lamprey system.

If the filter membrane is not saturated, you may repeat the tow/prefiltration/concentration steps to increase the quantity of captured material. A second filter membrane (duplicate sample) may be prepared as a backup for storage in your laboratory. If you choose to do so, do not apply a barcode sticker to the duplicate; simply label it manually with the same number, and make sure you order enough filter membranes (Membranes PC 10 μm Ø 47 mm - ref. TCTP04700 Millipore).

Remember to carefully fill the [log sheet](#) (see contextual data section below).

#Note: *You will each receive pieces of 2,000 μm mesh by mail, along with instructions on how to easily assemble a standardized sieving system. It is essential that all teams use the same mesh in order to ensure comparability across sampling sites.*

Blanks

To evaluate potential contamination of the Lamprey system during its use, please perform a blank filtration (*i*) after processing 15 samples (including those collected outside the collective time series), and (*ii*) at the end of the plankton time series.

A blank consists of pouring 300 mL of Milli-Q water into the Lamprey funnel and filtering it through a 10 μm pore-size membrane, following the standard filtration procedure. This blank should be performed prior to plankton sampling.

Please note that the Roscoff team will also participate in the collective plankton time series and will conduct blank filtrations after every two samples to enable a more detailed assessment of potential cross-contamination.

Contextual data

To properly interpret metabarcoding data, contextual environmental information is essential. Contextual data such as location, date, depth, etc. must be recorded on the logsheets; please refer to the detailed [instructions](#) for completing these forms.

Obtaining inter-calibrated physico-chemical measurements across 25 sites in Europe presents significant logistical challenges. Therefore, we only request that you measure water temperature—and, if feasible, salinity—during each sampling event. To do this, use a 10-Liter plastic bucket attached to a rope to collect subsurface water at the sampling site. Measure temperature and salinity directly from the water in the bucket. While different instruments may be used across sites to measure T and S, it is crucial to consistently use the same device throughout the seasonal sampling period at your location. This consistency will enable us to assess the temporal variability in temperature and salinity at each site. In a later phase, satellite-derived data — which are becoming increasingly accurate for coastal environments — could be utilized to contextualize our collective metagenetic dataset.

Of course you are free to measure other parameters, but they might not be used for the interpretation of the collective dataset. If you are equipped with a *Planktoscope*, we encourage you to perform quantitative imaging measurements on the same sample (note the dedicated space on the logsheet).

Sample storage and dispatch

Samples have to be stored at -20°C.

The sample will be sent at ambient temperature to the Station Biologique de Roscoff.

The first batch of samples will be sent midway through the sampling period (early 2026), with a second shipment at the end of the sampling period (summer 2026).

Sequencing

Sequencing will be performed at the Genoscope on Novaseq Illumina sequencer, with ~100,000 reads per marker and sample. We will target 3 markers: (i) JEDI (SSU rDNA V4V5); (ii) 18S V9; and (iii) COI. These cover, respectively: (i) prokaryotes and eukaryotes + their organelles; (ii) eukaryotes; (iii) eukaryotic mitochondria.

Data management plan (DMP)

Overview

The diagram above illustrates the various data and metadata generated throughout the project, along with their processing paths, methods, and repositories.

The following sections provide a description of the Data Management Plan (DMP), inspired by the Horizon Europe template. As the Lamprey workshops are part of the BIOcean5D project, this DMP is closely aligned with the BIOcean5D DMP, which is accessible at <https://zenodo.org/records/11262855>.

Overall Data Summary

The project will generate raw sequencing data (FASTQ files) and processed metabarcoding data (ASV tables in text format), along with associated meta/contextual-data (e.g., sampling location, date, temperature, and salinity) for each sampling event. We anticipate **a total of 728 sampling events**, corresponding to 28 samples (26 environmental samples plus two blanks) collected at **26 sites**, including Roscoff.

Each sample will be sequenced using three marker genes, resulting in 2,184 sequencing samples overall. Assuming an average of 100,000 reads per sample, the expected total raw data volume is approximately 30 GB, while the ASV tables are estimated to occupy around 30 MB. The size of the contextual metadata is negligible in comparison.

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Analysis of the ASV tables, derived from the raw FASTQ data, will provide insights into the seasonal succession of coastal plankton communities across Europe. Pan-european coastal plankton diversity across seasons can also be compared to baseline diversity measured along 115 land-to-sea transects using the same marker genes along the TREC expedition (<https://www.embl.org/about/info/trec/>), as well as to already existing metabarcoding data from European coastal plankton time-series. We hope to demonstrate the effectiveness of frugal monitoring tools for biodiversity/ecosystem assessment. Beyond the scope of this project, the dataset will be valuable to any researchers investigating coastal plankton dynamics and biodiversity.

FAIR data

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

By being deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), both the raw data and metadata will receive a persistent identifier. ASV tables will be assigned a DOI and list of all co-authors (listing all participants - to workshop, sampling, etc) upon submission to Zenodo and will use metadata persistent identifiers (BioSample) to name samples (e.g. <https://zenodo.org/records/14588202>).

Prior to publication on Zenodo, ASV tables and raw data will be made accessible to the collective effort contributors through the BIOcean5D data hub, for quality checkup and preliminary analyses. Direct download links will be provided upon request on Slack or by email.

Metadata submission to ENA as BioSamples will adhere to strict checklists, such as the ENA Micro B3 checklist. Search keywords, including plankton, metabarcoding, and time-series, will be added to the ASV table Zenodo records to enhance their discoverability. Metadata will be accessible at ENA (BioSamples) and will be easily retrievable through both API and website interfaces.

Making data accessible

Both ENA and Zenodo are trusted repositories that ensure data are assigned an identifier. In the case of Zenodo, this identifier will be a DOI.

The raw data will be made publicly accessible on ENA after undergoing quality checks by Genoscope. The ASV table will be published on Zenodo with an embargo until a scientific publication describing the results is submitted as a preprint.

Raw data and metadata will be accessible at ENA through direct download or via an API. ASV tables will be available for direct download on Zenodo.

There will be no restrictions on use.

Metadata will be openly available at BioSamples. The data will remain accessible for as long as they are hosted by ENA (40 years) and Zenodo (at least 20 years). However, there is no guarantee that metadata will still be available beyond these periods. All data are provided in text file formats (FASTQ and TSV), and no specific software is required to read them.

Making data interoperable

Raw data are provided in FASTQ format, the standard format used for sequencing data. Metadata will adhere to the Micro B3 standard. The ASV table, in text format, will also be converted into the Darwin Core format for direct submission to GBIF/OBIS. Where possible, metadata will utilise an ontology such as ENVO to describe the sample environment.

Increase data re-use

ASV tables are generated using the nf-core/ampliseq workflow, available on GitHub and Zenodo, and finalized with in-house scripts. These scripts will be accessible through GitLab repositories and published alongside the ASV tables on Zenodo. Additionally, a README document (in HTML format) is published together with the ASV table in Zenodo to provide detailed explanations on how the tables are constructed and the information they contain. The ASV tables will be licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0). The provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented in accordance with the MicroB3 ENA checklist.

Allocation of resources & Data security

During the analysis period, raw data and the ASV tables will be stored and backed up on the ABiMS cluster at Station Biologique de Roscoff (SBR). The associated costs (e.g., electricity, infrastructure) are covered by the ABiMS platform and SBR. No long-term preservation is planned on the ABiMS cluster; data will be preserved long-term and securely stored in trusted repositories, specifically EBI-ENA (raw data) and Zenodo (ASV tables), without incurring additional costs for the project.

Data ownership and sampling permits

The data generated and funded under the BIOcean5D Task 1.5 are jointly owned by the members of the BIOcean5D project and the external partners who contributed to their local acquisition. The objective of the Collective Plankton Time-Series initiative is to compare biodiversity patterns at the pan-European scale. Therefore, external partners agree to pool their local data for a pan-European meta-analysis. They also commit to obtaining the necessary local sampling permits, in accordance with European and international regulations. It is expected that these documents will be made available at the time of sample sending, in order to facilitate proper due diligence and compliance verification.

Bioinformatics

Raw data will be analysed with nf-core/ampliseq on ABiMS cluster using the following template: <https://gitlab.com/tara-expeditions-euk-metab/metab-workflow-template>

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Slack

Slack is a collaborative platform designed to facilitate communication within a working community. It allows users to organize discussions into thematic channels, share documents, ask questions, and follow conversations in a structured and accessible way. Within the framework of this project, Slack serves as the primary tool for information exchange between participants and the coordination team of this task.

As part of our collective plankton time-series initiative, we have created four dedicated Slack channels in the Plankton Planet workspace. All participants of the three workshops will receive individual invitations by email to join these channels. If you would like to involve additional members of your team, please contact us with the email address of the person you wish to include in the communication loop.

The four channels are the following one:

1- #welcome_lamprey :

This channel provides access to the Welcome Guide, which contains essential information to help you get started.

You are also invited to introduce yourself here and share a few words about your work, particularly your involvement with the Lamprey device. This space is intended to foster initial connections and build a sense of community among participants.

2- #dev_lamprey :

This channel is dedicated to sharing any suggestions, reflections, or feedback related to the design, use cases, and potential applications of the Lamprey device.

Feel free to contribute your ideas, raise questions, or propose improvements—this space is open for collective thinking and co-development.

3- #help_lamprey :

This channel is intended for any questions related to the use of the Lamprey device. Whether you need help with setup, protocols, troubleshooting, or data handling, feel free to ask here. The coordination team and other participants will do their best to assist you.

4- #biocean5d_lamprey :

This channel is dedicated to the BIOcean5D project and the collective plankton time-series initiative.

If you already have a Slack account, you just have to join the channels using the invitation received by email.

If you do not already have a Slack account, you will receive an invitation by email to join our Slack workspace. Simply click on the link provided in the message and follow these steps:

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1. Create a Slack account by entering your name and choosing a password.
2. You will then be redirected to the project's Slack workspace.
3. Once logged in, you will gain access to the dedicated discussion channels. Please make sure to enable notifications so you don't miss important updates.

No installation is required — Slack can be used directly in your web browser. A desktop app (Windows/Mac) and a mobile app (iOS/Android) are also available for more convenient access.

